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Viscoelastic bi-scale modeling of process-induced deformation in non-crimp fabric composite

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Process-induced residual stress in non-crimp fabric composites: experimental and numerical evaluation considering viscoelasticity (S. Koo and Y. Hoshikawa, et al., 2025, status: accepted)

Introduction: manufacturing composite materials and its problem

Fiber reinforced plastic (FRP)

✓ Manufacturing characteristics

Thermosetting resin

Cured (chemical reaction)

High reliability

Low productivity

Thermoplastic resin

Mold/Remold by heating

High productivity

Complex molding mechanism

Problems with FRP composites processing

✓ Process-induced residual stress → dimensional change

➤ **Thermomechanical mismatch** between layers, between fiber/matrix

➤ **Stress relaxation** by viscoelasticity

Can we predict?

Introduction: outline

- ✓ Mechanism investigation of process-induced deformation (**PID**) in NCF composites using **a bi-scale FEA**.
- ✓ **Different resin types** (thermosetting, thermoplastic) were compared and verified

TMA

DMA

Elastic fiber
Viscoelastic matrix

Resin properties

Homogenized

Micro-scale

lamina properties

Macro-scale

Experiment: NCF cross-ply laminate

Materials used

OR

+

Fiber tow
Stitch

DGEBA/4,4'-DDS
(Epoxy, thermosetting)

Nylon 6
(PA6, thermoplastic)

Cross-ply NCF

Cross-ply laminate of non-crimp fabric (NCF) composite

✓ 90° layer (top) ≠ 0° layer (bottom)

Necessary to consider resin-gap and viscoelasticity in evaluation of PID

Top layer

Bottom layer

Experiment: fabrication of NCF cross-ply laminate

Hot press (Toyoseiki, mini test press MP-WCL)

- Specimen: [90/0] cross-ply laminate, $100 \times 100 \text{ mm}^2$
- Method: hot press curing
- Measure PID with a 3D scanner

Pressure plate

Release film

Resin

NCF

Demold

PID

1. Cross-ply molding

2. Hot press curing

3. PID record

Scanned image

Experiment: evaluation of resin viscoelasticity with DMA test

Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA)

Material	Temperature	Frequency
Epoxy, PA6	25°C~220°C	0.1~10 Hz

- Construct master curve applying **time-temperature superposition principle (TTSP)**:

$$\log(t_{\text{ref}}) + \log(\alpha^T) = \log(t)$$

- Generalized Maxwell Model (GMM):

$$C_{ij}(t) = C_{ij}^0 - \sum_{k=1}^N C_{ij}^k \left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\alpha_{ij}^T \tau_{ij}^k}\right) \right]$$

t_{ref}	: Reference time
t	: Time of interest
α_{ij}^T	: Shift factor from reference temperature T_{ref}
$C_{ij}(t)$: Relaxation stiffness matrix
τ_{ij}^k	: Relaxation time
N	: Number of maxwell model parameter

10.0 x 50.0 x 1.0 mm³

DMA tension mode

DMA data to master curve

Stress update in periodic unit cell (PUC) analysis

Total stress:

$${}^t\sigma = {}^t\sigma^e - {}^t\sigma^v$$

$${}^{t_{n+1}}\sigma^e = {}^t\sigma^e + \mathbf{C}^e \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$$

$${}^{t_{n+1}}\sigma^v = {}^t\sigma^v + \Delta \mathbf{q}$$

Nonequilibrium stress increment $\Delta \mathbf{q}^k$ [1]:

$$\Delta \mathbf{q} = \sum_{k=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^6 \Delta q_{(m),ij}^k (t_{n+1})$$

Viscoelastic matrix

$$\Delta q_{m,ij}^k (t_{n+1}) = \left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta t}{\alpha_{ij}^T \tau_{ij}^k}\right) \right] \left[\mathbf{C}_{m,ij}^k \left(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_j(t_n) + \frac{\Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_j(t_{n+1})}{2} \right) - \Delta q_{m,ij}^k (t_n) \right]$$

t	: Time
dt	: Time increment
Δ	: Incremental component
σ	: Stiffness matrix
$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$: Internal force vector
$[]_m$: Matrix component
$[]_f$: Fiber component
$[]^e$: Elastic component
$[]^v$: Nonequilibrium component

Simulation: homogenized unidirectional (UD) viscoelastic properties

Fiber/Epoxy

Fiber/PA6

✓ **Smaller shift factor**
 ⇔ **Faster relaxation**

Simulation: stress distribution during PUC simulation

Fiber/Epoxy

- ✓ Faster relaxation
- ✓ Smaller amount of relaxation

Position	Relaxation amount
Near fiber	84%
Resin rich	97%

Application of homogenized properties to **PID prediction with macro-scale FEA**

Numerical model for PID simulation

- Quarter modeling (symmetry at $x = 0$ and $y = 0$)
- Boundary conditions: symmetry, fix base
- Mesh: 20-node Hex element

Cross-section view of NCF/Epoxy
($V_{f,tow}$: fiber-volume fraction)

Classical total Lagrangian method [2]

Implicit Newton-Raphson's scheme:

- **Cure shrinkage** and **thermal shrinkage**

$$\mathbf{K}^{(iter)} \Delta \mathbf{U}^{(iter)} = \mathbf{F}_{ex} - \mathbf{Q}_{int}^{(iter)} + \mathbf{Q}_{nm}$$

$$\mathbf{Q}_{nm} = \sum_e \int \mathbf{B}^T (\mathbf{C}^0 \Delta \mathbf{E}^{nm}) dV$$

$$\Delta \mathbf{E}^{nm} = \begin{cases} \Delta \mathbf{E}^{sh} = [\Delta E_1^{sh} & \Delta E_2^{sh} & \Delta E_3^{sh} & 0 & 0 & 0]^T \\ \Delta \mathbf{E}^{th} = [\Theta_1 \Delta T & \Theta_2 \Delta T & \Theta_3 \Delta T & 0 & 0 & 0]^T \end{cases}$$

\mathbf{Q}_{nm} : Non-mechanical internal force vector
 \mathbf{K} : Total stiffness matrix
 $\Delta \mathbf{U}$: Displacement vector
 \mathbf{F}_{ex} : External force vector
 \mathbf{Q}_{int} : Internal force vector
 $(iter)$: Newton-Raphson iteration
 n : Simulation steps

Stress update and consistent tangent matrix [1]

$$(\Delta S_i)^{(iter)}(t_{n+1}) = (\Delta S_i^e)^{(iter)}(t_{n+1}) - (\Delta S_i^v)^{(iter)}(t_{n+1})$$

$$\Delta S_i^e = C_{ij}^0 (\Delta E_j^e - \Delta E_j^{nm})$$

Same as PUC

$$D_{ij}^{(iter)}(t_{n+1}) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^N \left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta t}{\alpha_{ij}^T \tau_{ij}^k}\right) \right]$$

$S(t)$: 2nd Piola-Kirchhoff stress

$E(t)$: Green Lagrange strain

$D(t)$: Consistent tangent matrix

Quantitative/ Qualitative evaluation

NCF/Epoxy

NCF/PA6

Experiment: similar PIDs despite curing patterns

Simulation: validation of proposed model

Quantitative/ Qualitative evaluation

NCF/Epoxy

NCF/PA6

Experiment: similar PIDs despite curing patterns
FEA: well reproduced PIDs

Simulation: validation of proposed model

NCF/Epoxy

Residual stress development

Simulation: validation of proposed model

- Residual stress distribution
- ✓ **Localized stress in resin gap:** reaction force causes tensile stress
- ✓ **Out-of-plane PIDs:** shrinkage of 0° layer in y-direction

NCF/Epoxy

- **Experimental and bi-scale numerical FEA study on PID of thermosetting and thermoplastic NCF composites** were conducted
 - ✓ NCF resin-gap was captured in numerical model
 - ✓ Stress relaxation during processing was predicted using **pure resin** by GMM viscoelastic framework
- **Residual stress distribution** was reproduced by FEA, caused by thermomechanical mismatches
 - ✓ **The effect of thermal stress development and stress relaxation was captured**

1. Micro-scale analysis

2. Macro-scale analysis